

The Effectiveness Of The Organizational Performance Of Some Soccer Clubs (Professional League) In Jordan From The View Point Of Administrators, Coaches And Players

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 08 , 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 11, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Effectiveness, Organizational Performance, Administrators, Coaches, Players</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5564975</p>	<p><i>The objective of the study is to identify the effectiveness of the organizational performance of some soccer clubs in professional league in Jordan from the viewpoint of administrators, coaches and players working in them. For achieving this purpose, the researcher used a special measure after conducting the coefficients of validity and reliability. The study consisted of (67) administrators, coaches and players. After carrying out the appropriate statistical processing, one of the main results of the study was that the performance of the administrative bodies in some soccer clubs in professional league was at a very good level from the viewpoint of the study sample. The most important recommendations of the study were to pay attention to the views of the administrators, coaches and players, periodically and regularly evaluate the work of the administrative bodies and keep the administrative bodies of these soccer clubs informed of what is new in evaluating the organizational performance of sports institutions.</i></p>

Introduction

Sports clubs and sports organizations are considered an important part of developed communities. The sports clubs are a vital organization in communities in general in view of the services they provide to a large and very important sector, as they deal with the youth sector, which accounts for a large proportion of community. The sports clubs also provide cultural, social and sports activities on a voluntary basis. They contribute greatly to deepening the spirit of citizenship and sound upbringing as well as emphasizing the principles of tolerance, freedom of opinion and accepting the other's opinion.

The organizational performance is one of the most important administrative terms. The importance of this term is to identify the proper evaluation of the administrators of those sports institutions through their administrative work, leading to determine the fundamental administrative standards necessary for the success of the organization and identify the level of its performance and production (Davis & John 1997).

The evaluation process is essential and important since the supervisor shall continuously express his / her opinion (feedback) of subordinates and evaluate their acts and conducts within the sports institution within the constant and numerical standards and levels of performance as far as possible. In addition, the same role shall be given to subordinates in order to objectively evaluate their supervisors in a manner that is free from bias and personal opinion, which positively affects the development and progress of the institution (Alvesson, 2012).

The head of the sports organization and its members shall have a great wisdom and accept the other's opinion. They shall also have the ability to assess, measure and make judgments about the employee performance within the organization in order to improve or modify it. These judgments also contribute to identifying the strengths and the points that need continuously and periodically to be improved in the programs provided as well as encouraging employees to carry out the self-assessment process and activating the reward system in motivating the creative and outstanding staff (Dissler, 2003).

There are also many common methods to evaluate the employee performance in the sports institutions by using pre-prepared lists, recording important events or relying on the comparison among the employees, where the special computerized forms with certain fields directly related to the individual personality, habits, nature and other attributes are used. The supervisor will follow up these fields and develop them from time to time in proportion to the development of work, phase and future.

Although it is important to identify the level of performance of the organizations in developing and directing the enormous potential of the youth sector in the cultural, sports and social fields in these communities, we consider that a little and almost nonexistent attention is given to identifying the effectiveness of these sports institutions. The researcher also finds through his sports experience that these administrative bodies are formed based on personal relations and favoritism, making the work of these institutions ineffective and useless. The researcher

also suggests through his relationship with some sports clubs that there are no strict standards on the level of productivity within the sports clubs and the collective work performance to effectively achieve the work objectives.

Research Objectives:

1. Identifying the organizational performance of members of the administrative bodies in some soccer clubs from the viewpoint of administrators, coaches and players working in them.
2. Identifying the rank of some soccer clubs in professional league based on their organizational performance.
3. Identifying the differences among the views of members of the administrative bodies, coaches and players in evaluating the effectiveness of the performance of members of the administrative body of some soccer clubs

Study Questions:

- What is the level of the organizational performance of members of the administrative bodies in some soccer clubs in professional league from the viewpoint of their workers?
- What is the rank of some soccer clubs in professional league based on their organizational performance?
- Are there morally significant differences among members of the administrative bodies, coaches and players in evaluating the effectiveness of the performance of members of the administrative bodies of some soccer clubs in professional league ?

Research Determinants:

- 1. Human Determinant:** The study consisted of administrators, coaches and players of some soccer clubs in professional league.
- 2. Spatial Determinants:** The study was carried out in some soccer clubs in professional league
- 3. Temporal Determinants:** The study was carried out during the period January 5, 2019 until March 20, 2019.

Research Terminology:

Evaluation: a process of appraising something or assessing the performance of one phase of control. It focuses on valuing the results performed by individuals in a given work performance.

Member of the Administrative Body: a person who is elected by members of the General Assembly at a formal meeting.

Sports Club: a sports institution which aims at contributing to a positive role in the sports, social and cultural development of the community members within the needs and desires of its members, leading to achieving the philosophy of the country.

Coach: a qualified person who has educational, technical and administrative qualities to implement training programs.

Player: a person who has appropriate skills needed in a particular game, represents the club in participation in official sports events and is subject to the regulations and instructions of the club.

Administrator: a person who has the ability to manage one of the club activities and to spread the enthusiasm to the coach and the players in that activity.

Research Procedures:

The researcher has used the descriptive approach appropriate to the research objectives.

Research Sample and Population:

The research consisted of administrators, coaches and players of some soccer clubs in professional league, including Al wehdat sport club, Al faisali sport Club–Al Jazeera sport club, and Al ahli Sports Club, for the season (2019-2020).

The research sample was randomly selected from the members of the administrative bodies, coaches and players. There are (18) members of the administrative body, (26)coaches and (23)players with a total number(67) in the sports clubs(Al wehdat, Al faisali , Al jazeera, and Al ahli) with a percentage(65%) of the research population, as shown in Table (1).

Table (1): Research Sample

No.	Sports Club	Members of the Administrative Body	Coaches	Players	Total
1	Al Wehdat	4	6	6	16
2	Al Faisali	4	7	6	17
3	AL Jazeera	5	7	6	18
4	Al Ahli	5	6	5	16
Total		18	26	23	67

Research Tool:

In order to evaluate the performance of the administrative bodies, the researcher was required to design a preliminary form in light of the general framework of the subject matter. A measure was prepared and distributed to (15) community members, as their answers were limited to the most important qualities, acts and duties that shall be fulfilled in the performance of the administrative bodies. After relying on a number of previous studies and literature on this subject matter, the paragraphs of the measure were developed in accordance with the nature of the study.

Validity of the Measure:

In order to verify the validity of the paragraphs of the measure, it was presented to a group of competent experts to ascertain the validity of the paragraphs that need to be modified, added or deleted. The researcher obtained the percentage of agreement (87%) regarding the experts' opinions of the lowest paragraph. Then, the measure was adopted in its final form.

Reliability of the Measure:

The researcher adopted the (test and retest) method. It was applied to a sample of (10) members of the study population. The test was repeated after (two weeks) on the same sample and the same conditions using Pearson correlation coefficient to find the degree of relationship between the degrees of application I and II. It showed that the reliability coefficient was (91%), indicating that this correlation is at very good level in favor of the reliability of the measure.

Application of the Measure:

The measure was distributed in its final form to members of administrative bodies, coaches and players of the soccer clubs (Al Wehdat, Al Faisali, Al Jazeera and Al Ahli) in professional league. The responses of (67) members of the study sample (18) members of the administrative body, (26) coaches and (23) players were obtained. The responses of the study sample were sorted on the measure. After using the statistical methods appropriate to the nature of the study,

Statistical Methods:

The statistical methods were used in proportion to the nature of the study, as the analysis of variance (ANOVA), arithmetic mean, standard deviation, t - test and percentage of L.S.D were used.

Results and Discussion:

Table (2): Relative Ranking of the Performance of the Administrative Bodies from the Viewpoint of Coaches and Players.

No.	Theme	Percentages	Rank
1	Work orientation within the sports organization.	82 %	First
2	Administrative control and self-ability to comply with the work rules.	80 %	Second
3	Achieving the principle of justice in the sports organization.	79 %	Third
4	Dealing with others within the sports organization.	77 %	Fourth
5	Integration (motivation towards cooperation in completing the work phases)	75 %	Fifth
6	Belonging to the sports organization	74 %	Sixth
7	Conflict Management (the ability to solve sports problems within the sports organization)	74 %	Sixth
8	The use of the communication patterns at the work	73 %	Eighth
9	Enthusiasm towards assuming responsibility (self – initiative)	71 %	Ninth
10	Risk taking (creativity at work)	66 %	Tenth

By reviewing Table (2), the researcher suggests that the paragraph "work orientation within the sports organization" was in the first rank due to a strong contact between the members of the administrative body and the coaches in the sports club as well as the continuous work to guide the players through the daily work and the periodic continuous meetings in the sports club. The result is consistent with (Caerhant, 2009; Arthur, 2001).

In Table (2), the results showed that the administrative bodies have a great potential for control. The researcher indicates that the study sample is aware of the importance of orientation in the administrative body. He also points out that the administrative body is aware of its contribution to revealing the strengths and weaknesses that need to be improved as well as creating, preparing and developing the club programs in order to achieve positive results. This result is consistent with (Ivancevich & Gibson, 2005; Alvesson, 2012).

As shown in Table (2), the paragraph (Enthusiasm towards assuming responsibility (self – initiative)) was in the penultimate rank, followed by the paragraph (Risk taking (creativity at work)). The researcher indicates that some members of administrative bodies always try not to take responsibility for fear of mistakes that can be made, especially with regard to failures in the scores of sports teams, as some are trying to balm other administrators, coaches and players for those failures and low scores (Leonard & MacAdam 2002; Briner, 2014).

Table (3): Ranking of the soccer Clubs based on their Organizational Performance from the Viewpoint of their Workers.

No.	Sports Club	Percentage	Rank
1	Al Wehdat	81%	First
2	Al Ahli	77 %	Second
3	Al Faisali	73%	Third
4	Al Jazeera	67 %	Fourth

Table (3) shows that the results of four sports clubs were close together. The researcher indicates that members of the administrative bodies work in very similar manner and often have similar academic qualifications. They also rely on the first work experience and believe in the importance of raising morale and improving relations in a way that reflects on the results and achieves job satisfaction, which increases the concept of loyalty and belonging (Drucker,2006).

Table (4):Results of the One – Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of Responses to the Paragraphs of the Measure (Administrators, Coaches and Players)

Paragraph	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P
1	Between Groups	.24	2	.102	.171*	3.07
	Within Groups	63.197	106	.600		
	Total	63.573	107			
2	Between Groups	1.368	2	.670	1.29*	3.07
	Within Groups	55.50	107	.51		
	Total	65.018	109			
3	Between Groups	.136	2	.075	0.31*	3.07
	Within Groups	26.030	107	.24		
	Total	26.166	109			
4	Between Groups	1.466	2		2.858*	3.07
	Within Groups	26.400	107	.736		
	Total	27.866	109	.250		
5	Between Groups	.491	2	.245	0.734*	3.07
	Within Groups	35.759	107	.323		
	Total	36.250	109			
6	Between Groups	.475	2	5.240	1.020*	3.07
	Within Groups	50.920	107	.468		
	Total	51.395	109			
7	Between Groups	3.270	2	1.635	2.918*	3.07
	Within Groups	59.965	107	0.559		
	Total	63.235	109			
8	Between Groups	1.630	2	.815	1.234*	3.07
	Within Groups	51.130	107	.660		
	Total	52.760	109			
9	Between Groups	5.471	2	2.729	5.42*	3.07
	Within Groups	54.000	107	.500		

	Total	59.471	109			
10	Between Groups	1.560	2	.779	3.248*	3.07
	Within Groups	25.765	107	.264		
	Total	27.325	109			

As shown in Table (4), there were no morally significant differences among the responses of the study sample to the first paragraph (**work orientation within the sports organization**). The researcher indicated that the players are guided by the coaches and the administrative bodies through clear, effective and simple communication channels in order to implement activities and achieve the objectives. Arthur (2001) pointed out that the administrative hierarchy shall be interconnected and employees are positively directed without error trapping.

As shown in Table (4), there were no morally significant differences among the responses of the study sample to the second paragraph (**administrative control and self - ability to comply with the work rules**). From the viewpoint of the sample members, the members of the administrative bodies in all positions are interested in following up the reality of sports, cultural and social activities as well as trying to address the shortcomings and prevent mistakes. Cheese et al. (2007) pointed out that the majority of the acts and activities within the organization contribute significantly to enhance the sense of responsibility among employees towards their work in the organization.

As shown in Table (4), there were no morally significant differences among the responses of the study sample to the third paragraph (**the principle of justice in the sports organization**). From the viewpoint of the sample members, the administrative bodies deal fairly and regularly with mistakes and operates using incentives, rewards and punishment systems. Briner (2013) pointed out that the regulations and instructions applicable within the institution shall generally be clear and understandable in terms of bylaws related to incentives and punishment.

There were no morally significant differences among the responses of the study sample to the fourth paragraph (**dealing with others within the sports organization**). The researcher indicated that the administrative bodies often deal with the coaches and players as a family and consider the administrative body as the father who works hard and wisely in order to succeed his family. Schneider et al., 2013 pointed out that it is necessary to pay attention to providing a non - hostile competitive environment within the institution since each party wants to have a position contrary to the desire of the other party.

As shown in Table (4), there were no morally significant differences among the responses of the study sample to the fifth paragraph (**motivation towards cooperation in completing the work**). From the viewpoint of the sample members, the administrative bodies in these sports clubs carry out planning, controlling and decision-making, which provide appropriate conditions for an effective system to assess the work performance within the available possibilities. Arthur (2001) pointed out that the group leadership depends on predictability, influence and decision-making ability.

While Table (4) shows that there were morally significant differences among the responses of the study sample to the sixth paragraph (**belonging to the sports organization**), Table (5) shows results of the differences among the arithmetical means of the three groups (administrators, coaches and players) according to the sixth paragraph.

Table (5): Results of the Differences among the Arithmetical Means of the Three Groups (administrators, coaches and players) according to the Sixth Paragraph.

Group	Administrators (2.100)	Coaches (2.530)	Players (2.923)
Administrators (2.10)	_____	_____	_____
Coaches (2.530)	0.04331*	_____	_____
Players (2.923)	0.8367*	0.4140*	_____

The researcher indicated that some members of the administrative bodies are satisfied with the position only and consider it as a social position or that they avoid the concerns and problems of the club and appear only when achieving satisfactory results or in social celebrations. The reason behind this is the fear of making an administrative decision that leads to failures in the results and may be their attempt not to blame others for these consequences if any. Gardner (2006) pointed out that some administrative institutions are based on authoritarianism and have the position to satisfy old psychological diseases or to settle old accounts, keeping the labor productivity level low and emphasizing the need to change what is in the minds to achieve the best.

As shown in Table (4), there were no morally significant differences among the responses of the study sample to the seventh paragraph (**conflict management and ability to solve sports problems**). The researcher indicated that the members of the study sample are aware that the primary duties of the administrative bodies are to

manage conflicts within the sports club and provide an organizational climate based on justice among players, coaches and administrators to achieve their aspirations and desires. Altman and Hodgetts (1979) long pointed out that the change in roles and powers, the duplication of work or the difference in culture cause a low level of work and that the senior management shall early pay attention to these matters mentioned above.

There were no morally significant differences among the responses of the study sample to the eighth paragraph (**the use of the communication patterns at the work**). The research indicated that there is a clear communication hierarchy linking the senior management to the middle management to achieve the supervision, as the administrators provide reports and recommendations to the administrative body from the coaches and players and transfer decisions and orders of the administrative body to the players quickly and accurately. Alvesson, (2012) pointed out that it is necessary to provide an appropriate network within the organization, regardless of the size of the organizational structure, in order to achieve the work objectives accurately, quickly and clearly.

While Table (4) shows that there were morally significant differences among the responses of the study sample from their viewpoint, Table (6) shows results of the differences among the arithmetical means of the three groups (administrators, coaches and players) according to the ninth paragraph.

Table (6): Results of the Differences among the Arithmetical Means of the Three Groups (administrators, coaches and players) according to the Ninth Paragraph.

Group	Administrators (2.2310)	Coaches (2.880)	Players (2.310)
Administrators (2.2310)	_____	_____	_____
Coaches (2.880)	1.5222*	_____	0.3890*
Players (2.310)	0.1560*	_____	_____

There were morally significant differences among the responses of the study sample to the ninth paragraph (**enthusiasm towards assuming responsibility**). The research indicated that some members of the administrative bodies in various administrative positions may not be qualified to assume responsibility, not realize the importance of taking responsibility in sports work, or keep themselves away from problems and disagreements and even a low level of the different club activities. Altman and Hodgetts (1979) pointed out that the passive competition among workers to hold positions creates a kind of initial conflict, leading to the emergence of human groupings against others as well as apathy which results in disappointment.

While Table (4) shows that there were morally significant differences among the responses of the study sample to the tenth paragraph (**creativity at work and risk taking**), Table (7) shows results of the differences among the arithmetical means of the three groups (administrators, coaches and players) according to the tenth paragraph.

Table (6): Results of the Differences among the Arithmetical Means of the Three Groups (administrators, coaches and players) according to the Tenth Paragraph.

Group	Administrators (2.680)	Coaches (2.831)	Players (2.822)
Administrators (2.680)	_____	_____	_____
Coaches (2.831)	_____	_____	_____
Players (2.822)	0.31*	_____	_____

According to the researcher, the players suggested from their viewpoint that some members of the administrative bodies may perform their classic routine work or that they only provide the fundamental requirements without thinking to provide creative and innovative conditions that help the sports clubs in advancing and keeping up with administrative development in other clubs. Plewa (2009) pointed out that the institutions with culturally and scientifically inconsistent groups or incoherent groups may not tend to creativity. These groups at work focus only on performing the work fundamentals without having any aspect of creativity or innovation.

Conclusions:

- The performance of the administrative bodies in some soccer clubs in professional leagues was at a very good level from the viewpoint of the study sample.
- While there were no morally significant differences among administrators, coaches and players in (7) paragraphs, there were morally significant differences in (3) paragraphs, including sixth, ninth and tenth paragraphs.

Recommendations:

1. Paying attention to the opinions of administrators, coaches and players in evaluating the performance of the administrative bodies of sports clubs in various sports activities.

2. Keeping the administrative bodies informed of what is new in evaluating the organizational performance of any institution.
3. Encouraging Public Assembly to test members of the administrative bodies with the ability to predict well, have the leadership and creativity, and make decisions.
4. Encouraging these sports clubs to evaluate the performance of sports clubs periodically and regularly.
5. Conducting a similar study involving other soccer sports clubs in professional league and making comparisons to identify the causes.

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